

Sparse Randomised Projections for CS-CDMA MIMO radar

Saravanan Nagesh^a, Maria A. Gonzalez-Huici^a, and Joachim Ender^{a,b}

^aFraunhofer FHR

^bUniversität Siegen

Abstract

This paper presents an innovative solution to tackle challenges associated with elevated range sidelobes and computational complexity in the context of Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) and Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) radar systems. The solution involves the incorporation of Sparse Randomized Projections (SRP) as an efficient approach for 2D Compressive Sensing (CS) MIMO radar.

1 Introduction

MIMO radar systems generate substantial data due to simultaneous transmission and reception across multiple channels, intensifying computational demands, particularly in imaging applications influenced by system configuration, processing algorithms, and application-specific requirements. An essential factor for managing computational load is selecting the right signal processing pipeline. Typically, parallel processing pipelines, optimized algorithms, and hardware acceleration are employed for standard configurations. However, the potential to tailor MIMO systems to match specific application needs with reduced computational load is often overlooked, highlighting MIMO radar systems' configurational flexibility. One promising aspect in the field of MIMO radar is the CDMA (Code Division Multiple Access) MIMO radar system, representing a significant advancement. These systems merge the foundational principles of CDMA, initially developed for communication, with the spatial diversity and beamforming capabilities of MIMO radar technology. The key to achieving orthogonality in CDMA MIMO radar lies in the use of unique orthogonal codes, which enable multiple transmission elements to cooperate seamlessly within the same frequency range without causing interference. These codes are commonly referred to as phase-modulated waveforms due to their adjustment of the radar signal's phase component. However, it's crucial to acknowledge that, despite their remarkable capabilities, CDMA MIMO radar systems introduce challenges, especially in real-world scenarios. These challenges arise from elevated sidelobes, which can lead to sidelobe-cluttered radar scenes, ultimately masking targets.

Compressed Sensing (CS) effectively mitigates sidelobes in radar systems by exploiting the sparsity inherent in many radar scenes. Rather than relying solely on conventional signal processing techniques that may introduce sidelobes, CS takes advantage of the fact that radar scenes often contain sparse or compressible information. By intelligently selecting a limited number of measurements, CS reconstructs the radar scene using mathematical optimization al-

gorithms [1]. In Figure 1, a scene reconstruction comparison between conventional methods and a CS-based Basis Pursuit algorithm is shown. The CS-based reconstruction demonstrates superior performance compared to Matched Filtering (MF) and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), which suffer from significant sidelobes, as clearly seen when compared to the ground truth.

Therefore, this study delves into the exploration and potential application of CS techniques [2] for CDMA MIMO radars, with an emphasis on effectively addressing these challenges and inherent issues in the systems while aiming to achieve optimum performance through reliable reconstruction.

Conventionally, CS-based radar systems employ irregular sampling as opposed to regular Nyquist sampling to facilitate sparse reconstruction techniques [1]. However, it is worth noting that in both cases, the total number of samples remains constant. What differs is the rate of sampling, either in the temporal or spectral domains, or the number of sampled elements in the spatial domain. The complete potential of CS reconstruction can only be realized when considering the possibilities of achieving improved results, such as enhanced resolution or reduced errors, while using fewer samples and irregular sampling rates.

In general, the number of targets to be estimated is related to the number of required samples, which, in turn, helps synthesize the target scene. Borrowing concepts from Finite-Rate-of-Innovation (FRI) Sampling, as stated in [3], 2D Range-Azimuth radar scenes are typically sparse [2]. Therefore, if we assume that the maximum possible number of targets for a fixed scene (field of view) is known, it becomes possible to reduce the number of samples needed while keeping the number of target hypotheses to estimate the unknowns the same.

In this study, we propose a novel two-stage algorithm: first, we sparsify the data domains, followed by the injection of incoherency achieved through mutual coherence minimization. This concept is termed 'Sparsifying Randomized Projections' (SRP) and is designed to optimize signal acquisition efficiency and achieve accurate reconstruction. We apply SRP to a generic CDMA MIMO radar signal

Figure 1 Image Reconstruction for CDMA MIMO using conventional and CS based methods.

model with some assumptions regarding its field of view to explore the advantages of efficient signal acquisition and reconstruction. SRP plays a pivotal role in this context by efficiently selecting a subset of measurements to capture the essential information, leading to reduced computational complexity and faster signal reconstruction.

2 Signal Model

Consider a MIMO radar system that utilizes N_T transmit antennas and N_R receive antennas. It is assumed that the distance between the elements is small enough to ensure a complete correlation of the radar echo from a particular scatterer across the array, implying a coherent propagation scenario. We assume a monostatic radar configuration for transmit and receive arrays (collocated MIMO) and far field. Let the receiver and transmitter array characteristics be described by their respective array manifolds as, $\mathbf{a}_R(\beta)$ and $\mathbf{a}_T(\beta)$, where $\beta = \cos(\theta)$, is the direction of arrival (DoA). For convenience, we formulate the analysis in terms of delay τ instead of range r . There is no loss of generality as delay and range are related by $\tau = 2r/c$, with c denoting the speed of light. All notions for Doppler have been ignored, as the focus of this study is limited to fast time (single period), hence we concentrate only on the delay-azimuth domain.

Consider that each i^{th} transmit element radiates a single complex envelope modulated with a unique sequence of length L . Let the time period of each bit be T_c , and its corresponding bandwidth be B_c . Transmit orthogonality is achieved within a single period, which is equivalent to fast time. Consequently, the received signal at the j^{th} receiver, depending on the target parameters, can be approximated as

$$\mathbf{y}_j = e^{i2\pi c\lambda^{-1}\tau\delta_\tau} e^{i2\pi \mathbf{d}_R \beta \delta_\beta(j-1)} \sum_{i=1}^{N_T} e^{i2\pi \mathbf{d}_T \beta \delta_\beta(i-1)} \mathbf{T}_\tau \mathbf{s}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{N_t} \quad (1)$$

where, \mathbf{T}_τ is a circulant shift matrix representing all shifted versions of the transmitted signal, such that $[\mathbf{T}_\tau \mathbf{s}]_k = [\mathbf{s}]_{k-\tau}$, and $k-\tau$ stands for subtraction modulo N_t . Hence, as a result of the periodicity operator \mathbf{T}_τ and the periodic influence of β as in (1), the maximum possible grid points

that can be achieved is bounded by $N_T N_R N_t$.

Next, we consider the generic model for the presence of multiple targets, which is given by

$$\mathbf{y}_j = \sum_{k=1}^K \rho_k e^{i2\pi c\lambda^{-1}\tau_k\delta_\tau} \left[e^{i2\pi \mathbf{d}_R \beta_k \delta_\beta(j-1)} \sum_{i=1}^{N_T} e^{i2\pi \mathbf{d}_T \beta_k \delta_\beta(i-1)} \mathbf{T}_{\tau_k} \mathbf{s}_i \right] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_t} \quad (2)$$

where $k = 1, \dots, K \forall \mathbb{N}$, is the number of targets and ρ_k its corresponding reflectivity.

Let $\mathbf{a}_\gamma^j \in \mathbb{C}^{N_t}$ be a vector of target parameters corresponding to every j^{th} receiver, such that

$$\mathbf{a}_\gamma^j = e^{i2\pi \mathbf{d}_R \beta \delta_\beta(j-1)} \sum_{i=1}^{N_T} e^{i2\pi \mathbf{d}_T \beta \delta_\beta(i-1)} \mathbf{T}_\tau \mathbf{s}_i \quad \forall \gamma \in (\tau, \beta) \quad (3)$$

This allows the possibility of rewriting (2) efficiently as

$$\mathbf{y}_j = \sum_{k=1}^K \rho_k e^{ik_0\tau_k\delta_\tau} \mathbf{a}_{\gamma_k}^j \quad (4)$$

Therefore, any target scene imaged by this system can be considered a vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^N$, where $N = N_T N_R N_t$, being supported by indices of γ_k , which correspond to parameters of the target. Each nonzero entry of this vector \mathbf{x} is occupied by a reflectivity, corresponding to the parameters of the targets, given by

$$\mathbf{x}_{\gamma_k} = \rho_k e^{ik_0c\tau_k\delta_\tau} \quad (5)$$

Finally, by collecting all signals from N_R receivers, we form a vector $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{C}^M$, where $M = N_R N_t$. Then, we define a discrete grid target parameter space for the considered MIMO configuration. The grid space takes into consideration all possible delay samples and angular hypotheses with respect to each receiver element. By stacking each delay sample in combination with each azimuth as in (3), we form a matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N}$.

$$\mathbf{A}_\gamma = ((\mathbf{a}_\gamma^1)^T, (\mathbf{a}_\gamma^2)^T, \dots, (\mathbf{a}_\gamma^{N_R})^T)^T \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N} \quad (6)$$

Therefore the linear relationship between the measurements collected from the MIMO system for a given target scene response \mathbf{x} can be efficiently represented as

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R N_t} \quad (7)$$

where, $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ is a vector of measurements, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$, is a sparse vector with target coefficients, $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is a vector of additive noise, and $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N}$ is the **sensing matrix**. We, thus have a highly under-determined system (13), (as $M \ll N$) from which the target parameters (lying on the support set of \mathbf{x}) have to be reconstructed. This can be made possible via the use of CS algorithms

2.1 Problem Formulation

In theory, the effective bandwidth of a signal refers to the range of frequencies or data rates needed to accurately represent the signal without significant loss of information. The choice of signal processing techniques, such as sampling rate, filtering, and compression, can influence the required bandwidth. CS-based reconstruction allows for sampling the effective bandwidth of a signal at reduced irregular data rates (fewer random samples) while maintaining signal fidelity [1].

2.1.1 Under Sampling Projections

When considering the MIMO angular domain, the effective spatial bandwidth is related to the virtual aperture of the MIMO radar. This can be calculated as the sum of the Tx and Rx apertures. If we consider that the transmit array elements are placed at positions $p_v, \forall v = 1, \dots, N_T$, and the receive array elements are placed at positions $p_q, \forall q = 1, \dots, N_R$, then, along the axis of measurement, the virtual aperture can be expressed as,

$$L_{vir} = \max_{v,q} (p_v + p_q) - \min_{v,q} (p_v + p_q) \quad (8)$$

Therefore, the resolution of the spatial domain Δu can be given by $1/L_{vir}$, or if considered in terms of the number of elements $L_{vir}/N_T N_R$.

If $p_v + p_q$ passes through all natural numbers from $1, \dots, B$ where $B = N_T N_R$, the synthesized virtual array is a Uniform Linear Array (ULA).

When considering the number of angular parameters that can be estimated by the array configuration, it is limited by the number of array elements. In scenarios where the observed scene exhibits sparsity, the ULA configuration can become redundant, providing an opportunity to reduce the number of measurements through element reduction[4].

Consider the MIMO signal model described in Equation 13, with the assumption of limiting the search to one range bin. Consequently, the signal model reduces to a classic Direction of Arrival (DOA) estimation problem. Let us assume that the scene consists of a fixed number of targets, denoted as K , such that $K < B$. The effective aperture is fixed by pre-defining the maximum and minimum values of p_v and p_q resulting in equal spacing B elements.

The objective would be to find the optimal number and positions for the array elements to best discretize the domain,

given the sparsity of the scene as a prior information [4]. The problem can be formulated as

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \left| F(u_k) - \sum_{n=1}^N v_n e^{j2\pi d_n u_k} \right| < \eta \quad (9)$$

where, $F(u_k)$ is the angular pattern due to the k^{th} directional cosine, η is the error tolerance in obtaining this solution and v_n are the excitation related to elements present at positions d_n and u_k corresponds to the direction cosine. The problem in matrix notation is written as

$$\mathbf{y}(\theta) = \mathbf{A}(\theta)\mathbf{x}_{pos} \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{y}(\theta)$ is a vector of angular measurements with a pattern resulting from the superposition of all K targets, $\mathbf{A}(\theta)$ is a square DFT matrix of size $B \times B$ elements, and \mathbf{x}_{pos} is the vector of positions occupied by the uniform array.

Since we are considering prior knowledge of the scene, we can formulate the problem as an iterative weighted l_1 norm minimization, with the weights corresponding to the positions occupied by the elements, calculated with respect to every possible realization of the scene. The objective is to find the sparsest combination \mathbf{w} , provided that P positions are occupied, such that $K \leq P < B$. The problem can be formulated as follows,

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos} = \min_x [\|\mathbf{W}\mathbf{x}_{pos}\|_1 + \beta \|\mathbf{A}(\theta)\mathbf{W}\mathbf{x}_{pos} - \mathbf{y}(\theta)\|_2] \quad (11)$$

where, $\mathbf{W} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{w})$, such that $\mathbf{w}_{itr} = 1/\mathbf{x}_{pos_{itr}} + \zeta$, with ζ as a marginal error.

The solution results in the sparsest combination of P array elements, discretizing the predefined aperture. Which is backtracked to the relative N_R elements as N'_R such that $N'_R < N_R$.

2.1.2 Random Projections

Besides sparsity, another criterion is that the associated sensing matrix must satisfy the Restricted Isometric Property (RIP)[2]. The RIP guarantees the recovery performance of a given sensing matrix. Unfortunately, validating the RIP is an NP-hard problem, and this theoretical metric is not practical for real-world purposes. An alternative to the RIP is mutual coherence, which is defined as,

$$\mu(\mathbf{A}) \triangleq \max_{i \neq j} \frac{|\mathbf{a}_i^H \mathbf{a}_j|}{\|\mathbf{a}_i\| \|\mathbf{a}_j\|} \quad (12)$$

We demonstrated in previous research [5] that the selection of waveforms and arrays with random configurations enhances the incoherence of the sensing matrix, contributing to an overall improvement in the performance of the MIMO radar system.

Building upon the concepts explored in our previous studies [6], we are considering waveform parameters as optimizable variables for mutual coherence minimization. The objective is to find the optimum combination of phase components to be transmitted so that the resulting sensing matrix has low mutual coherence. This objective is formulated as an optimization problem, as given below:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_{\mathbf{z}} \quad \|\mathbf{z}\|_{\infty} \\
& \text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{z} = \max_{i \neq j} \frac{|\psi_i(\phi_i)^H \psi_j(\phi_j)|}{\|\psi_i(\phi_i)\| \|\psi_j(\phi_j)\|} \\
& \quad \phi \in \{0, 2\pi\} \\
& \quad \mathbf{z} \in \{g_{11}, \dots, g_{nn-1}\}
\end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Here, \mathbf{z} represents the upper triangular elements of a Gram matrix given by $\mathbf{G} = |\mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A} - \mathbf{I}|$, and $\psi_i(\phi_i)$ is the i^{th} column of \mathbf{A} with the corresponding intrapulse phase component ϕ . For details about the mutual coherence minimization algorithm, interested authors are requested to refer to [6].

Taking into consideration both sparsity and mutual coherence, we can reformulate the signal model as shown in Equation 14:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{P} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{C}^{N'_R N_t} \quad (14)$$

Here, \mathbf{P} represents a projection matrix that incorporates element reduction along the rows and incoherency along the columns of the sensing matrix \mathbf{A} .

This matrix plays a crucial role in reducing the number of elements and introducing randomness into the transmitted signals. As a result, it enhances signal reconstruction performance and significantly reduces computational load.

3 Numerical Simulations

Consider a MIMO radar with an aperture 25λ , let $N_T = 3$ be fixed for simplicity and the approximate number of receiver is calculated as $N_R = 17$. The initial TX and RX arrays are configured as an ULA with $d_T = N_R 0.5\lambda$ and $d_R = 0.5\lambda$. Consider a CDMA transmission scheme with orthogonality in Fast time using a generic Hadamard sequence of $L = 32$. The resultant RA sensing matrix is of size $N_R N_t \times N_u N_T$.

3.1 Sparsification Step

We restrict the problem to a DOA search grid, considering only a single range bin. Consequently, the sensing matrix reduces to an $N_T N_R \times N_T N_R$ square Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) matrix. Since we use a Uniform Linear Array (ULA) configuration, this matrix is invertible. We assume a fixed sparsity in the scene, set to a maximum of 6 targets.

The ULA configuration is provided as input to the iterative weighted l_1 minimization algorithm mentioned in Equation 11. The weight vector is initialized as a vector of ones, marking all positions as occupied and having a total weight of $\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{vir}}} w_i$. We conduct Monte Carlo (MC) simulations consisting of 1000 runs, simulating all possible realizations of the scene with the predefined number of targets. The average the weights over every MC cycle for each target realisation converges the weights towards the optimal positions. Figure 2 depicts the input and output array configurations passed to the algorithm, while Figure 3

Figure 2 The figure presents a comparison of the resulting array with reduced elements achieved through weighted l_1 minimization, based on the given input array. In the figure, * denotes transmitter positions, \circ represents receiver positions, and \diamond signifies virtual positions.

Figure 3 The figure illustrates the reduction in the sum of weights for the elimination of each redundant position in the ULA.

illustrates the iterative reduction of weights throughout the entire simulation.

The solution to the problem provides an estimate of optimal positions on the virtual array, which is then translated back to physical RX array elements by performing a combinatorial search.

To evaluate the proposed array scheme, we perform 1D estimation with 6 targets under conditions of closely spaced, widely spaced, and varying signal strengths. We use classical MF, FFT, and CS-based Basis Pursuit Denoising. The results are presented in Figure 4. We can see in both cases the CS based recovery out performs conventional methods. The resultant sparse array, with N'_r where $N'_r < N_r$, is now adopted as the new configuration for designing the 2D RA sensing matrix. The Sparsification stage has successfully achieved a 47% reduction in measurements.

The next stage is to enhance the reconstruction efficiency

Figure 4 Target estimation comparison: Full vs. Reduced Array. Evaluating MF, FFT, and BPDN for separated (Top) and closely spaced (Bottom) target configurations.

of the algorithm by making the columns of the sensing matrix highly incoherent. This is achieved through the proposed mutual coherence minimization step in Equation 13.

3.2 Mutual coherence minimisation

After reducing redundant data in the first stage, we apply our MC minimization algorithm from [6] to the augmented sensing matrix. This algorithm iteratively optimizes intra-pulse phases until it achieves a lower MC value, resulting in optimized poly-phase sequences with reduced sidelobes and improved correlation properties. Figure 8 presents a comparison of the Gram matrices between the input and output sequences, highlighting a reduction in correlation within the hypothesis of the sensing matrix.

Furthermore, in Figures 6, 7, and 5 we demonstrate the enhanced reconstruction performance resulting from the optimized sensing matrix. We compute metrics such as recovery percentage \hat{x}/x_{true} and recovery error $|\hat{x} - x|^2$ for different numbers of targets and varying SNR values.

4 Conclusion

In this study, we introduced a two-stage algorithm called 'Sparsifying Randomized Projections' (SRP), designed to sparsify data domains and minimize mutual

Figure 5 Comparison of improvement in recovery percentage (Probability of success) for the initialised sensing matrix and Optimised sensing matrix

coherence for enhancing signal acquisition efficiency and reconstruction accuracy. We applied this concept to a CDMA MIMO radar system, assuming a predefined sparsity level. Our analysis revealed a significant reduction

in redundant data and an improvement in reconstruction performance in the augmented system model compared to the initial model, validating the effectiveness of SRP for MIMO radar systems.

Figure 6 Reconstruction comparison over varying SNR

Figure 7 Reconstruction comparison over varying Sparsity

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6 Literature

[1] D. L. Donoho, "Compressed sensing," in *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 1289-1306, April 2006, doi: 10.1109/TIT.2006.871582

Figure 8 Comparison of Gram Matrices, obtained reduction factor of 0.39

[2] J. Ender, "A brief review of compressive sensing applied to radar," 2013 14th International Radar Symposium (IRS), Dresden, Germany, 2013, pp. 3-16.

[3] Kumar Vijay Mishra, and Yonina C. Eldar (2018). Sub-Nyquist Radar: Principles and Prototypes. CoRR, abs/1803.01819.

[4] G. Oliveri, M. Donelli and A. Massa, "Linear Array Thinning Exploiting Almost Difference Sets," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 57, no. 12, pp. 3800-3812, Dec. 2009, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2009.2027243 .

[5] S. Nagesh, J. Ender and M. A. González-Huici, "Influence of Waveform Orthogonality and Array Geometry on Compressed Sensing Algorithms for CDMA MIMO Radar," 2022 14th German Microwave Conference (GeMiC), Ulm, Germany, 2022, pp. 76-79.

[6] S. Nagesh, J. Ender and M. A. González-Huici, "Array Position Optimisation for Compressed Sensing MIMO Radar based on Mutual Coherence Minimisation," 2022 23rd International Radar Symposium (IRS), Gdansk, Poland, 2022, pp. 98-103, doi: 10.23919/IRS54158.2022.9904978 .